

Technical Report on Task B of EFSA's priority pest mandate (M-2022-00070): Data for supporting shortlisting of Union Quarantine Pests

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Alexandre Nougadère, Roumiana Krusteva, Daria Rzepecka and Sybren Vos

Abstract

In 2022, EFSA was mandated by the European Commission (EC) to support the EC's Joint Research Centre (JRC) of Sevilla in the prioritisation of the Union Quarantine Pests (UQPs). This mandate is articulated in three different tasks to provide data that are scientifically sound on pest ecology (hosts and spread) and impact on hosts. Task A aimed to provide a list of the host plants of the UQPs. Task B was dedicated to support the JRC in shortlisting the UQPs considering their spread and impact. Task C will be targeted at providing a set of parameters for the Impact Indicator for Priority Pests (I2P2). I2P2, developed and run by the JRC will finally provide EC and Member States with a reasoned ranking of all candidate priority pests. In this report, EFSA describes the approach and methodology developed under Task B and the type of data provided to JRC for shortlisting the UQPs.

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Key words: Union quarantine pests, candidate priority pests, host range, ranking, spread score

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Correspondence: plants@efsa.europa.eu

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1 Introduction

In the EFSA mandate M-2022-00070, the European Commission (EC, DG SANTE) requested EFSA to provide scientific and technical support to DG JRC:

- *"for the analysis of all Union Quarantine pests (UQPs) (hosts for all UQPs)"* (Task A)
- *"when shortlisting candidate priority pests, including the assessment of the spread and impact (in line with EFSA's quantitative risk assessment methodology)"* (Task B).

In relation to Task A, in December 2022 the EFSA work on listing the possible hosts of all the UQPs was delivered and resulted in more than 11.500 pest-host combinations. Following the application to these pest host combinations of the ranking approach developed by the JRC, a preliminary ranking of pests resulting from the estimation of the economic and environmental impact was provided. However, this preliminary screening delivered results that are not supported by the current general knowledge and existing evidence on the top ranked pest species. Two main reasons could explain this:

- For each pest-host combination, it is assumed that the impact corresponds to a total loss in production. However, the impact that a pest can cause on a given host can vary from very minor to extremely high (with the complete destruction of the crop) depending on a number of aspects connected to pest and host biology, ecoclimatic conditions, type of product;
- Scientific names of the plant species are required to match with the nomenclature and commercial categories used in EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT (e.g. production and price). However, EFSA pest-host combinations are provided at plant species level as obtained from the scientific evidence (publications and databases) and this matching with statistical categories is not always possible due to: a) different level of aggregation, b) translation of common names applied in stats to specific taxonomic identities, c) absence of many plant species, also of economic relevance, such as ornamental species.

Following these preliminary results from Task A, in Task B EFSA was tasked to further support the JRC integrating spread and impact data to retain a shortlist that will allow to perform a more accurate analysis of the economic and environmental impacts.

The purpose of the analysis presented in this report is to further support the JRC in the shortlisting of 30 new pests in addition to the 28 candidate priority pests assessed in 2019, out of 395 UQPs¹. EFSA proposes an approach using five criteria to address the uncertainties described above. In addition, the integration of more information on impact and spread for each pest could allow a more informed and accurate ranking of the pests.

The different scenarios presented in this report were shared and discussed with the JRC and DG SANTE during two meetings held on 12 September 2023 and on 30 October 2023.

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32021R2285>

2 Method

To achieve Task B, EFSA collected data on the regulated taxonomic entities as UQPs, in particular on their vector capacity, on the host plants for which impact was reported, and on the spread mechanisms that are relevant. In this context, EFSA proposed the use of **five criteria** described below to reduce the number of pests and pests-host combinations that would be retained for further analysis by the JRC. This information was collected in an Excel file provided to the JRC Sevilla. In the section 3, this report describes the use of the 5 criteria under 3 different scenarios.

- **Criterion 1: Exclusion of the 2019 candidate priority pests**

The 28 candidate priority pests from 2019 are excluded from the analysis, in order to address only new UQPs. This is applied as the 2019 candidate priority pests (Table 1) are already under review as part of Task C and therefore included by default to the final shortlist.

Table 1: The 2019 Candidate Priority Pests (exclusion criterion 1)
<i>Agrilus anxius</i>
<i>Agrilus planipennis</i>
<i>Anastrepha ludens</i>
<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>
<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>
<i>Anthonomus eugeni</i>
<i>Aromia bungii</i>
<i>Bactericera cockerelli</i>
<i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i>
<i>Bactrocera zonata</i>
<i>Bretziella fagacearum</i> *
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>
<i>Candidatus Liberibacter</i> spp., causal agent of citrus Huanglongbing or citrus greening
<i>Clavibacter sepedonicus</i> *
<i>Conotrachelus nenuphar</i>
<i>Dendrolimus sibiricus</i>
Grapevine Flavescence dorée phytoplasma *
<i>Phyllosticta citricarpa</i>
<i>Popillia japonica</i>
<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> *
<i>Rhagoletis pomonella</i>
<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>
<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i> *
<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>
<i>Thrips palmi</i> *
<i>Tilletia indica</i> *
<i>Xanthomonas citri</i> pv. <i>citri</i> and pv. <i>aurantifolii</i> *
<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>

* pests not included in the final list of 20 priority pests in the current EC regulation²

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32019R1702>

- **Criterion 2: Exclusion of macrogroups**

The EU legislation includes 395 taxonomic entities that are regulated, for majority of them, at species level (or below), and others at genus and even family level.

For some of the ones regulated at genus or family level, the number of plants that can potentially host at least one species of the taxonomic group can be very high thus biasing the shortlisting of pests regulated at species level.

Therefore, the macrogroups listed in Table 2 are excluded.

Table 2: Macrogroups of pests (exclusion criterion 2)
<i>Adrama</i> spp.
<i>Anastrepha</i> spp.
<i>Arceuthobium</i> spp.
<i>Atropellis</i> spp.
<i>Bactrocera</i> spp.
<i>Begomoviruses</i>
<i>Ceratitis</i> spp.
<i>Cronartium</i> spp.
<i>Dacus</i> spp.
<i>Draeculacephala</i> sp.
<i>Eutreta</i> spp.
<i>Gymnocarena</i> spp.
<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp.
<i>Hirschmanniella</i> spp.
<i>Monochamus</i> spp. (non-European populations)
<i>Procecidochores</i> spp.
<i>Rhagoletis</i> spp.
<i>Scolytinae</i> spp. (non-European)
<i>Strauzia</i> spp.
<i>Zeugodacus</i> spp.

• **Criterion 3: Exclusion of vectors without direct impact**

Pests that are regulated due to their vectoring capacity but that are known not to have a direct impact on host plants are excluded. Therefore, the vector species listed in Table 3 are excluded.

Table 3: Vectors without direct impact (exclusion criterion 3)
<i>Acrogonia citrina</i>
<i>Acrogonia virescens</i>
<i>Aphrophora angulata</i>
<i>Aphrophora permutata</i>
<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> Genn. (non-European populations) known to be vector of viruses
<i>Bothrogonia ferruginea</i>
<i>Bucephalogonia xanthopis</i>
<i>Ceratothripoides claratris</i>
<i>Clasteroptera achatina</i>
<i>Clasteroptera brunnea</i>
<i>Cuernia costalis</i>
<i>Cuernia occidentalis</i>
<i>Cyphonia clavigera</i>
<i>Dechacona missionum</i>
<i>Dilobopterus costalimai</i>
<i>Draeculacephala minerva</i>
<i>Draeculacephala</i> sp.
<i>Ferrariana trivittata</i>
<i>Fingeriana dubia</i>
<i>Friscanus friscanus</i>
<i>Graphocephala atropunctata</i>
<i>Graphocephala confluens</i>
<i>Graphocephala versuta</i>
<i>Helochara delta</i>
<i>Hishimonus phycitis</i>
<i>Homalodisca ignorata</i>
<i>Homalodisca insolita</i>
<i>Homalodisca vitripennis</i>
<i>Lepyronia quadrangularis</i>
<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>
<i>Macugonalia cavifrons</i>
<i>Macugonalia leucomelas</i>
<i>Molomea consolidata</i>
<i>Monochamus</i> spp. (non-European populations)
<i>Myndus crudus</i>
<i>Neokolla hieroglyphica</i>
<i>Neokolla severini</i>
<i>Oncometopia facialis</i>
<i>Oncometopia nigricans</i>

<i>Oncometopia orbona</i>
<i>Oragua discoidula</i>
<i>Pagaronia confusa</i>
<i>Pagaronia furcata</i>
<i>Pagaronia trecedecempunctata</i>
<i>Pagaronia triunata</i>
<i>Parathona gratiosa</i>
<i>Pityophthorus juglandis</i>
<i>Plesiommata corniculata</i>
<i>Plesiommata mollicella</i>
<i>Poophilus costalis</i>
<i>Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus</i>
<i>Pseudopityophthorus pruinosis</i>
<i>Sibovia sagata</i>
<i>Sonesimia grossa</i>
<i>Tapajosa rubromarginata</i>
<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>
<i>Trioza erytraeae</i>
<i>Xiphinema americanum</i>
<i>Xiphinema bricolense</i>
<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>
<i>Xiphinema inaequale</i>
<i>Xiphinema intermedium</i>
<i>Xiphinema rivesi</i> (non-EU populations)
<i>Xiphinema tarjanense</i>
<i>Xyphon flaviceps</i>
<i>Xyphon fulgida</i>
<i>Xyphon triguttata</i>

- **Criterion 4: Exclusion of pest-host combinations for plants without reported impact**

According to the definition of Art. 6 of Regulation (EU) 2016/2031, the “priority pests are the ones for which “their potential economic, environmental or social impact is the most severe in respect of the Union territory [...]”, therefore the pests to prioritise are those able to cause damage to the plants.

However, ISPM 5 (2023) defines host range as:

“*Species capable, under natural conditions, of sustaining a specific pest or other organism*”. This definition of host plants does not integrate the concept of impact or damage caused by a pest.

In this context EFSA identified, for each regulated pest, the host plants for which observed impact is reported. Different sources of information were consulted for each pest and the search was ended when robust information was found.

- (i) The EFSA publications were consulted as first, due to their technical scope in supporting EU phytosanitary legislation. Text review and data extraction were

performed on EFSA outputs in the following sequence a) Pest categorisations, b) Pest risk assessments, c) Pest survey cards.

- (ii) If the required information was not retrieved from the EFSA publications, further sources were consulted, in the following sequence: a) National Risk Assessments, b) CABI Compendium, c) EPPO Pest Risk Analysis.

Furthermore, EPPO classifies certain hosts as “major host” based on the following definition:

“Major host: a host plant which is important for the pest, or on that plant the pest is considered to be important. This category is assigned by the EPPO Secretariat, resulting from a qualitative judgement, and using available information (e.g. the plant is frequently considered in the literature as an important host, significant damage is observed). The fact that the host status has been demonstrated (full cycle, Koch’s postulate completed) or that the plant is a preferred host (choice studies) will be indicated together with the bibliographic references whenever data is available.”

For all UQPs, information on major hosts was extracted from EPPO Global database and is provided in a separate column. This information is used for guiding further searches in case of pests with very few references but is not used further in this exclusion criterion.

Each pest-host combination occupies a separate row: with the application of this exclusion criterion, all the pest-host combinations for which no observed impact have been reported are filtered out. However, the sources reporting impact do not always provide information on the type and magnitude of the damages caused by the pest and could vary for example from the seasonal damage on leaves of a tree with no effect on the commercial value of the related production to the death of the tree with the complete elimination of the related production.

Table 4: Pests with no reported impact (exclusion criterion 4)

<i>Acidiella kagoshimensis</i>
<i>Acidoxantha bombacis</i>
<i>Acleris nivisellana</i>
<i>Acleris robinsoniana</i>
<i>Acleris senescens</i>
<i>Acroceratitis distincta</i>
<i>Acrogonia citrina</i>
<i>Acrogonia virescens</i>
<i>Adrama</i> spp.
American plum line pattern virus
<i>Anastrepha</i> spp.
Andean potato mild mosaic virus
<i>Aphrophora angulata</i>
<i>Aphrophora permutata</i>
<i>Asimoneura pantomelas</i>
<i>Austrotephritis protrusa</i>
<i>Bactrocera latifrons</i>
<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> Genn. (non-European populations) known to be vector of viruses
<i>Bistrispinaria fortis</i>

<i>Bistrispinaria magniceps</i>
<i>Bothrogonia ferruginea</i>
<i>Bucephalogonia xanthopis</i>
<i>Callistomyia flavilabris</i>
<i>Campiglossa albiceps</i>
<i>Campiglossa californica</i>
<i>Campiglossa duplex</i>
<i>Campiglossa reticulata</i>
<i>Campiglossa snowi</i>
<i>Carpomya incompleta</i>
<i>Carpomya pardalina</i>
<i>Ceratothripoides claratris</i>
Chilli leaf curl virus
<i>Choristoneura carnana</i>
<i>Choristoneura lambertiana</i>
<i>Choristoneura occidentalis biennis</i>
<i>Choristoneura occidentalis occidentalis</i>
<i>Choristoneura orae</i>
<i>Choristoneura pinus</i>
<i>Choristoneura retiniana</i>
Citrus chlorotic spot virus
<i>Clasteroptera achatina</i>
<i>Clasteroptera brunnea</i>
Cowpea mild mottle virus
<i>Craspedoxantha marginalis</i>
<i>Cuerna costalis</i>
<i>Cuerna occidentalis</i>
<i>Cyphonia clavigera</i>
<i>Dacus</i> spp.
<i>Dechaona missionum</i>
<i>Dilobopterus costalimai</i>
<i>Dioxya chilensis</i>
<i>Dirioxa pornia</i>
<i>Draeculacephala minerva</i>
<i>Draeculacephala</i> sp.
<i>Elsinoë citricola</i>
<i>Euleia separata</i>
<i>Euphranta camelliae</i>
<i>Euphranta canadensis</i>
<i>Euphranta cassia</i>
<i>Euphranta japonica</i>
<i>Euphranta oshimensis</i>
<i>Eurosta solidaginis</i>
<i>Eutreta</i> spp.
<i>Ferrariana trivittata</i>
<i>Fingeriana dubia</i>

<i>Friscanus friscanus</i>
<i>Gastrozona nigrifemur</i>
<i>Goedenia stenoparia</i>
<i>Graphocephala atropunctata</i>
<i>Graphocephala confluens</i>
<i>Graphocephala versuta</i>
<i>Gymnocarena</i> spp.
<i>Helochara delta</i>
<i>Hishimonus phycitis</i>
<i>Homalodisca ignorata</i>
<i>Homalodisca insolita</i>
<i>Homalodisca vitripennis</i>
<i>Insizwa oblita</i>
<i>Lepyronia quadrangularis</i>
<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>
<i>Lopholeucaspis japonica</i>
<i>Macugonalia cavifrons</i>
<i>Macugonalia leucomelas</i>
<i>Marriottella exquisita</i>
Melon yellowing-associated virus
<i>Molomea consolidata</i>
<i>Monacrostichus citricola</i>
<i>Monochamus</i> spp. (non-European populations)
<i>Myndus crudus</i>
<i>Neaspilota alba</i>
<i>Neaspilota reticulata</i>
<i>Neokolla hyeroglyphica</i>
<i>Neokolla severini</i>
Non-EU isolates of potato viruses S, X and Potato leafroll virus
<i>Oncometopia facialis</i>
<i>Oncometopia nigricans</i>
<i>Oncometopia orbona</i>
<i>Oragua discooidula</i>
<i>Pagaronia confusa</i>
<i>Pagaronia furcata</i>
<i>Pagaronia tredecimpunctata</i>
<i>Pagaronia triunata</i>
<i>Paracantha trinotata</i>
<i>Parastenopa limata</i>
<i>Paratephritis fukaii</i>
<i>Paratephritis takeuchii</i>
<i>Paraterellia varipennis</i>
<i>Parathona gratiosa</i>
<i>Philophylla fossata</i>
<i>Pissodes cibriani</i>
<i>Pissodes fasciatus</i>

<i>Pissodes punctatus</i>
<i>Pissodes zitacuarensis</i>
<i>Pityophthorus juglandis</i>
<i>Plesiommata corniculata</i>
<i>Plesiommata mollicella</i>
<i>Poophilus costalis</i>
Potato virus B
<i>Procecidochares</i> spp.
<i>Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus</i>
<i>Pseudopityophthorus pruinosis</i>
<i>Ptilona confinis</i>
<i>Ptilona persimilis</i>
<i>Rhagoletis</i> spp.
<i>Rioxoptilona dunlopi</i>
<i>Sibovia sagata</i>
<i>Sonesimia grossa</i>
<i>Sphaeniscus binoculatus</i>
<i>Sphenella nigricornis</i>
<i>Strauzia</i> spp.
Sweet potato chlorotic stunt virus
Sweet potato mild mottle virus
<i>Taomyia marshalli</i>
<i>Tapajosa rubromarginata</i>
Temperate fruit decay-associated virus
<i>Tephritis leavittensis</i>
<i>Tephritis luteipes</i>
<i>Tephritis ovatipennis</i>
<i>Tephritis pura</i>
Tomato chocolate virus
Tomato marchitez virus
Tomato mild mottle virus
<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>
<i>Toxotrypana curvicauda</i>
<i>Toxotrypana recurcauda</i>
<i>Trioza erytrae</i>
<i>Trupanea bisetosa</i>
<i>Trupanea femoralis</i>
<i>Trupanea wheeleri</i>
<i>Trypanocentra nigrithorax</i>
<i>Trypeta flaveola</i>
<i>Urophora christophi</i>
<i>Xanthaciura insecta</i>
<i>Xiphinema americanum sensu stricto</i>
<i>Xiphinema bricolense</i>
<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>
<i>Xiphinema inaequale</i>

<i>Xiphinema intermedium</i>
<i>Xiphinema rivesi</i> (non-EU populations)
<i>Xiphinema tarjanense</i>
<i>Xyphon flaviceps</i>
<i>Xyphon fulgida</i>
<i>Xyphon triguttata</i>
<i>Zacerata asparagi</i>
<i>Zonosemata electa</i>

• **Criterion 5: Minimum spread score**

To reduce further the number of pest-host combinations, an additional criterion can be used. In each pest categorisation, the mechanisms of spread of the pest are briefly described, distinguishing between natural and human-assisted spread. Given the relevance of this parameter also for the I2P2 ranking method, this information was therefore extracted (Table 5) following the same search strategy as applied for Criterion 4, consulting primarily the EFSA pest categorisations.

Table 5: Spread score calculation per pest (spread mechanism and coefficient)

Filter 5: Spread capacity													
Natural spread							Human assisted spread					Total	
Vector or carrier needed		Flight		Natural means			Short distance In field movement Machinery and tools	Long distance Beyond field					
Present in the EU	Absent from the EU	Good flyer	Not good	Airborne: wind-rain	Pollen	Soil or waterborne		Hitckiking	P4P & Seeds	Fruits & vegetables	Wood products	Max	
5	1	5	1	3	2	1	2	5	5	2	2	34	

The information was extracted giving '1' to all the spread mechanisms relevant to a given pest, otherwise '0' was given. A coefficient/weight (from 1 to 5) is assigned to each spread mechanism following experts' discussion, as indicated in the lower line of Table 5. These weights for the different spread mechanisms were agreed to reflect the relative importance and contribution of each spread mechanism to the potential spread capacity for the scrutinized pests.

Weight	Contribution to potential spread of the pests
1	Very low
2	Low
3	Medium
4	high
5	Very high

In this way, to describe this spread capacity, a spread score is obtained for each pest: the spread score of a given pest is the sum of the weighted values of the spread mechanisms. This spread score is used solely for the relative ranking of the pests and their prioritisation regarding the spread mechanisms. Applying a threshold for the spread score allows to extract a specific list of pests as shown in section 3.1.Results

Three main scenarios are detailed below following the application of the five criteria and varying the minimum spread scores (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Frequency distribution according to the criteria and minimum spread score applied including the **three scenarios presented below**

Scenario 1: Minimum spread score of 11

The aim of this scenario is to reduce as much as possible the number of pest-host combinations that are retained as relevant for further scrutiny. A minimum spread score of 11 includes the 2019 candidate priority pests (except *Tilletia indica*) and include therefore all the 20 current priority pests in the Regulation (EU) 2019/1702³. A minimum spread score of 12 would not be inclusive enough (missing some current priority pests with a spread score of 11) and a minimum spread score of 10 would not be selective enough. Therefore, the following results are established by applying the criteria one to five described previously, and a minimum spread score of 11.

A list of **57 UQPs** results from this scenario (Table 6). The corresponding 125 pest-host combinations are listed in Annex 1 with a list of 84 host plants with observed impact (Table 7) that could be used for further analysis by the JRC for ranking the associated pests based on economic and environmental impact.

In addition to this new list, the 28 candidate priority pests assessed in 2019 could be evaluated by EFSA in the Task C of the current mandate.

Table 6: UQPs with a minimum spread score of 11

Pests (n=57)	Spread Score
<i>Acleris gloverana</i>	13
<i>Acleris issikii</i>	13
<i>Acleris minuta</i>	15
<i>Acleris nishidai</i>	13
<i>Acleris semipurpurana</i>	13
<i>Acleris variana</i>	13
<i>Aleurocanthus citriperdus</i>	11
<i>Aleurocanthus spiniferus</i>	11
<i>Aleurocanthus woglumi</i>	11
Andean potato latent virus	16
<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i>	11
<i>Anthonomus quadrigibbus</i>	12
<i>Anthonomus signatus</i>	11
<i>Botryosphaeria kuwatsukai</i>	11
<i>Ceratocystis platani</i>	13
Cherry rasp leaf virus (CRLV)	12
Cherry rosette virus	12
<i>Choristoneura conflictana</i>	13
<i>Choristoneura fumiferana</i>	13
<i>Choristoneura parallela</i>	15
<i>Choristoneura rosaceana</i>	13
<i>Coniferiporia sulphurascens</i>	11
<i>Coniferiporia weirii</i>	11

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32019R1702>

Pests (n=57)	Spread Score
<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	11
<i>Elsinoë australis</i>	11
<i>Elsinoë fawcettii</i>	11
<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	18
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Albedinis</i>	11
<i>Geosmithia morbida</i>	12
Grapevine berry inner necrosis virus	12
Grapevine vein-clearing virus	12
<i>Grapholita packardii</i>	11
<i>Helicoverpa zea</i>	13
<i>Keiferia lycopersicella</i>	12
<i>Oemona hirta</i>	12
<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	14
Peach rosette mosaic virus	12
<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> (non-EU isolates)	16
<i>Pissodes nemorensis</i>	17
<i>Pissodes nitidus</i>	17
<i>Pissodes strobi</i>	17
<i>Pissodes terminalis</i>	17
<i>Pissodes yunnanensis</i>	17
<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>	17
<i>Pomacea</i>	12
Potato black ringspot virus	14
Potato virus H	14
Potato virus T	11
<i>Prodioplosis longifila</i>	11
<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	11
<i>Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum</i>	11
<i>Scirtothrips citri</i>	11
<i>Scirtothrips dorsalis</i>	12
<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	13
<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	13
Tobacco ringspot virus	12
<i>Unaspis citri</i>	11

Table 7: Host plants with a reported impact of UQPs with a minimum spread score of 11

Host plants
<i>Abies balsamea</i>
<i>Abies</i> spp.
<i>Amelanchier alnifolia</i>
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>botrytis</i>
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>capitata</i>
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>
<i>Cedrus</i> spp.
<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>
<i>Citrus limon</i>
<i>Citrus limonia</i>
<i>Citrus reticulata</i>
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>
<i>Citrus</i> spp.
<i>Coniferus</i>
<i>Cupressus</i> spp.
<i>Diospyros kaki</i>
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>
<i>Glycine max</i>
<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i>
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.
<i>Juglans regia</i>
<i>Juglans nigra</i>
<i>Juniperus bonsai</i>
<i>Juniperus chinensis</i>
<i>Larix kaempferi</i>
<i>Malus domestica</i>
<i>Malus</i> sp.
<i>Malus</i> spp.
<i>Mangifera indica</i>
<i>Nicotiana</i> spp.
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>
<i>Oryza sativa</i>
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>
<i>Picea sitchensis</i>
<i>Picea</i> spp.
<i>Pinaceae</i>

Host plants
<i>Pinus contorta</i>
<i>Pinus elliotii</i>
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>
<i>Pinus koraiensis</i>
<i>Pinus luchuensis</i>
<i>Pinus muricata</i>
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>
<i>Pinus pinea</i>
<i>Pinus radiata</i>
<i>Pinus</i> spp.
<i>Pinus strobus</i>
<i>Platanus orientalis</i>
<i>Platanus</i> spp.
<i>Poncirus trifoliata</i>
<i>Populus tremuloides</i>
<i>Populus</i> spp.
<i>Prunus avium</i>
<i>Prunus cerasus</i>
<i>Prunus domestica</i>
<i>Prunus persica</i>
<i>Prunus salicina</i> x <i>simonii</i>
<i>Prunus</i> sp.
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>
<i>Pyrus communis</i>
<i>Pyrus</i> sp.
<i>Pyrus</i> spp.
<i>Quercus</i> sp.
<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i>
<i>Rosa</i> spp.
<i>Rubus</i> sp.
<i>Salix miyabeana</i>
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>
<i>Solanum melongena</i>
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>
<i>Thuja</i> spp.
<i>Tsuga heterophylla</i>
<i>Ulex europaeus</i>

Host plants
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>
<i>Vaccinium</i> sp.
<i>Vitis</i> spp.
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>
<i>Zea mays</i>
<i>Zea mays</i> convar. <i>saccharata</i>

Scenario 2: Minimum spread score of 7

The aim of this scenario is to select the UQPs that would correspond to a list of about 200 host plants with reported impact.

All Criteria one to five described previously with a minimum spread score of 7 (instead of 11) were applied to retain 196 host plants with reported observed impact (Table 9), corresponding to **143 UQPs** (Table 8) and 356 pest-host combinations listed in Annex 2.

From this list of 143 UQPs, 30 pests could be extracted following a ranking based on economic and environmental impact. In addition to this new list, the 28 candidate priority pests assessed in 2019 could be evaluated by EFSA in the Task C of the current mandate.

However, using this strategy, compared to scenario 1, more uncertain correspondences will be established between the host list extracted from the literature by EFSA and the databases from EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT.

Table 8: UQPs with a minimum spread score of 7 (n=143)

Pests (n=143)	Spread score
<i>Acleris gloverana</i>	13
<i>Acleris issikii</i>	13
<i>Acleris minuta</i>	15
<i>Acleris nishidai</i>	13
<i>Acleris semipurpurana</i>	13
<i>Acleris variana</i>	13
<i>Acrobasis pyrivorella</i>	8
<i>Aleurocanthus citriperdus</i>	11
<i>Aleurocanthus spiniferus</i>	11
<i>Aleurocanthus woglumi</i>	11
Andean potato latent virus	16
Andean potato mottle virus	10
<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	9
<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i>	11
<i>Anthonomus grandis</i>	10
<i>Anthonomus quadrigibbus</i>	12
<i>Anthonomus signatus</i>	11

Pests (n=143)	Spread score
<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	9
<i>Apriona cinerea</i>	8
<i>Apriona germari</i>	8
<i>Apriona rugicollis</i>	8
<i>Arrhenodes minutus</i>	8
Black raspberry latent virus	7
Blueberry leaf mottle virus	7
<i>Botryosphaeria</i>	11
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma pruni</i> -related strain (North American grapevine yellows, NAGYIII)	10
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma pruni</i> -related strains (Clover yellow edge, Potato purple top Akpot7, MT117, Akpot6; PPT-COHP, -GTOP)	10
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma pyri</i> -related strain (Peach yellow leaf roll)	10
<i>Carposina sasakii</i>	9
<i>Ceratocystis platani</i>	13
Cherry rasp leaf virus (CRLV)	12
Cherry rosette virus	12
Cherry rusty mottle associated virus	7
Cherry twisted leaf associated virus	7
<i>Choristoneura conflictana</i>	13
<i>Choristoneura fumiferana</i>	13
<i>Choristoneura parallela</i>	15
<i>Choristoneura rosaceana</i>	13
Chrysanthemum stem necrosis virus	10
<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	8
CiLV-C	10
CiLV-C2	10
CiLV-N sensu novo	10
Citrus strain of OFV	10
Citrus tristeza virus (non-EU isolates)	10
Coconut cadang-cadang viroid	7
<i>Coniferiporia sulphurascens</i>	11
<i>Coniferiporia weirii</i>	11
<i>Davidsoniella virescens</i>	9
<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	9
<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	9
<i>Diabrotica virgifera zea</i>	9
<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	11
<i>Elsinoë australis</i>	11
<i>Elsinoë fawcettii</i>	11
<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	9
<i>Euwallacea fornicatus sensu lato</i>	8
<i>Exomala orientalis</i>	7
<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	18
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Albedinis</i>	11
<i>Geosmithia morbida</i>	12
<i>Globodera pallida</i>	10
<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	10
Grapevine berry inner necrosis virus	12
Grapevine red blotch virus	8
Grapevine vein-clearing virus	12
<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	8
<i>Grapholita packardii</i>	11
<i>Grapholita prunivora</i>	9
<i>Guignardia loricata</i>	8
<i>Helicoverpa zea</i>	13

Pests (n=143)	Spread score
HGSV-2	10
<i>Keiferia lycopersicella</i>	12
<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	9
<i>Massicus raddei</i>	8
<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	8
<i>Melampsora medusae</i> f. sp. <i>Tremuloidis</i>	8
<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	10
<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>	8
<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i> Karssen	10
<i>Mycodiella laricis-leptolepidis</i>	8
<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	8
<i>Nemorimyza maculosa</i>	9
<i>Neocosmospora euwallaceae</i>	7
<i>Neoleucinodes elegantalis</i>	8
<i>Oemonia hirta</i>	12
<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	14
Peach mosaic virus	8
Peach rosette mosaic virus	12
<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	10
<i>Phyrdenus muriceus</i>	9
<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> (non-EU isolates)	16
<i>Pissodes nemorensis</i>	17
<i>Pissodes nitidus</i>	17
<i>Pissodes strobi</i>	17
<i>Pissodes terminalis</i>	17
<i>Pissodes yunnanensis</i>	17
<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>	17
<i>Pomacea</i>	12
Potato black ringspot virus	14
Potato virus H	14
Potato virus P	7
Potato virus T	11
Potato yellow dwarf virus	10
Potato yellow mosaic virus	10
Potato yellow vein virus	10
Potato yellowing virus	10
<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp.	9
<i>Prodiplosis longifila</i>	11
<i>Pseudocercospora angolensis</i>	10
<i>Pseudocercospora pini-densiflorae</i>	9
<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	11
<i>Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum</i>	11
<i>Ralstonia syzygii</i> subsp. <i>Celebesensis</i>	7
<i>Ralstonia syzygii</i> subsp. <i>Indonesiensis</i>	7
<i>Rhigopsidius tucumanus</i>	9
<i>Rhynchophorus palmarum</i>	10
<i>Ripersiella hibisci</i>	7
<i>Saperda candida</i>	8
<i>Scirtothrips aurantii</i>	9
<i>Scirtothrips citri</i>	11
<i>Scirtothrips dorsalis</i>	12
<i>Septoria malagutii</i>	9
<i>Sphaerulina musiva</i>	10
<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	10
<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	13
Squash vein yellowing virus	10

Pests (n=143)	Spread score
<i>Stagonosporopsis andigena</i>	9
<i>Stegophora ulmea</i>	8
Strawberry chlorotic fleck-associated virus	10
Strawberry leaf curl virus	10
<i>Tecia solanivora</i>	9
<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	13
Tobacco ringspot virus	12
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus	10
Tomato mosaic Havana virus	10
Tomato mottle Taino virus	10
Tomato ringspot virus	10
Tomato severe rugose virus	10
Tomato yellow vein streak virus	10
<i>Trirachys sartus</i>	8
<i>Unaspis citri</i>	11
<i>Venturia nashicola</i>	10

Table 9: Host plants with an observed impact of UQPs with a minimum spread score of 7 (n=196)

<i>Abies balsamea</i>
<i>Abies</i> spp.
<i>Acer negundo</i>
<i>Acer saccharum</i>
<i>Alnus rhombifolia</i>
<i>Amelanchier alnifolia</i>
<i>Apium graveolens</i>
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>
<i>Beta vulgaris</i> subsp. <i>vulgaris</i>
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>botrytis</i>
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>capitata</i>
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>
<i>Castanea crenata</i>
<i>Castanea mollissima</i>
<i>Castanea sativa</i>
<i>Cedra</i> spp.
<i>Celtis sinensis</i>
<i>Chrysanthemum</i> spp.
<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>
<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>
<i>Citrus limon</i>
<i>Citrus limonia</i>
<i>Citrus reticulata</i>
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>
<i>Citrus</i> spp.
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>
<i>Coniferus</i>
<i>Corylus avellana</i>
<i>Cucumis melo</i>
<i>Cucumis melo</i> var. <i>flexuosus</i>
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>
<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>

<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>
<i>Cuphea</i> spp.
<i>Cupressus</i> spp.
<i>Daucus carota</i>
<i>Diospyros kaki</i>
<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>
<i>Enkianthus perulatus</i>
<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>
<i>Fabaceae</i>
<i>Fagus crenata</i>
<i>Fagus</i> spp.
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>
<i>Fragaria</i> spp.
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>
<i>Fragaria virginiana</i>
<i>Glycine max</i>
<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i>
<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.
<i>Helianthus annus</i>
<i>Hibiscus</i> spp.
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>
<i>Juglans regia</i>
<i>Juglans nigra</i>
<i>Juniperus bonsai</i>
<i>Juniperus chinensis</i>
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>
<i>Larix decidua</i>
<i>Larix kaempferi</i>
<i>Larix laricina</i>
<i>Larix occidentalis</i>
<i>Larix</i> spp.
<i>Liriodendron</i> spp.
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>
<i>Malus baccata</i>
<i>Malus domestica</i>
<i>Malus prunifolia</i>
<i>Malus pumila</i>
<i>Malus</i> sp.
<i>Malus</i> spp.
<i>Mangifera indica</i>
<i>Medicago sativa</i>
<i>Morus</i> spp.
<i>Nicotiana</i> spp.
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>
<i>Oryza sativa</i>
<i>Pelargonium</i> spp.
<i>Persea americana</i>
<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>
<i>Phoenix</i> spp.
<i>Picea engelmannii</i>
<i>Picea pungens</i>
<i>Picea sitchensis</i>
<i>Picea</i> spp.
<i>Pinaceae</i>
<i>Pinus caribaea</i>
<i>Pinus contorta</i>

<i>Pinus densiflora</i>
<i>Pinus elliottii</i>
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>
<i>Pinus koraiensis</i>
<i>Pinus luchuensis</i>
<i>Pinus merkusii</i>
<i>Pinus muricata</i>
<i>Pinus nigra</i>
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>
<i>Pinus pinea</i>
<i>Pinus radiata</i>
<i>Pinus</i> spp.
<i>Pinus strobus</i>
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>
<i>Pinus thunbergii</i>
<i>Platanus acerifolia</i>
<i>Platanus orientalis</i>
<i>Platanus racemosa</i>
<i>Platanus</i> spp.
<i>Poncirus trifoliata</i>
<i>Populus tremuloides</i>
<i>Populus</i> × <i>canadensis</i>
<i>Populus alba</i>
<i>Populus deltoides</i>
<i>Populus euphratica</i>
<i>Populus nigra</i> × <i>maximowiczii</i>
<i>Populus</i> spp.
<i>Populus talassica</i>
<i>Populus tremuloides</i>
<i>Populus</i> × <i>euroamericana</i>
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>
<i>Prunus avium</i>
<i>Prunus cerasus</i>
<i>Prunus domestica</i>
<i>Prunus dulcis</i>
<i>Prunus persica</i>
<i>Prunus persica</i>
<i>Prunus salicina</i>
<i>Prunus salicina</i> × <i>simonii</i>
<i>Prunus</i> sp.
<i>Prunus</i> spp.
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>
<i>Psidium guajava</i>
<i>Punica granatum</i>
<i>Pyrus bretschneideri</i>
<i>Pyrus communis</i>
<i>Pyrus pyrifolia</i> var. <i>culta</i>
<i>Pyrus ussuriensis</i>
<i>Pyrus</i> sp.
<i>Pyrus</i> spp.
<i>Quercus acuta</i>
<i>Quercus acutissima</i>
<i>Quercus aliena</i>
<i>Quercus dentata</i>
<i>Quercus liaotungensis</i>
<i>Quercus mongolica</i>
<i>Quercus robur</i>
<i>Quercus robur</i> subsp. <i>pedunculiflora</i>

<i>Quercus serrata</i>
<i>Quercus</i> sp.
<i>Quercus</i> spp.
<i>Quercus variabilis</i>
<i>Ricinus communis</i>
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>
<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i>
<i>Rosa</i> spp.
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>
<i>Rubus</i> sp.
<i>Salix acmophylla</i>
<i>Salix aongarica</i>
<i>Salix laevigata</i>
<i>Salix miyabeana</i>
<i>Salix turanica</i>
<i>Scorzonera hispanica</i>
<i>Serissa</i> spp.
<i>Solanum betaceum</i>
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>
<i>Solanum melongena</i>
<i>Solanum quitoense</i>
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>
<i>Theobroma cacao</i>
<i>Thuja</i> spp.
<i>Tsuga canadensis</i>
<i>Tsuga heterophylla</i>
Turf grasses
<i>Ulex europaeus</i>
<i>Ulmus glabra</i>
<i>Ulmus laevis</i>
<i>Ulmus minor</i>
<i>Ulmus pumila</i>
<i>Ulmus</i> spp.
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>
<i>Vaccinium</i> sp.
<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>
<i>Vitis labrusca</i> cv. <i>Concord</i>
<i>Vitis</i> spp.
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>
<i>Zea mays</i>
<i>Zea mays</i> convar. <i>Saccharata</i>
<i>Zelkova serrata</i>
<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i>

Scenario 3: All spread scores

Another scenario discussed in September 2023 between EFSA and the EC is presented here. The criterion 5 “spread score” is not used to filter out pest-host combinations.

A list of **189 UQPs** is obtained (Table 10) corresponding to **445 pest-host combinations** (listed in Annex 3), with a total of **219 host plants with an observed impact** (Table 11).

For these pests, in the JRC model for ranking the pests, their spread score will be considered as well as the economic data of the related hosts plants i.e. estimation of the value of production and area at risk (Cf. related JRC report).

Table 10: UQPs with reported impact disregarding the spread scores (n=189)

Pest	Spread score
<i>Acleris gloverana</i>	13
<i>Acleris issikii</i>	13
<i>Acleris minuta</i>	15
<i>Acleris nishidai</i>	13
<i>Acleris semipurpurana</i>	13
<i>Acleris variana</i>	13
<i>Acrobasis pyrivorella</i>	8
<i>Aleurocanthus citriperdus</i>	11
<i>Aleurocanthus spiniferus</i>	11
<i>Aleurocanthus woglumi</i>	11
Andean potato latent virus	16
Andean potato mottle virus	10
<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	9
<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i>	11
<i>Anthonomus grandis</i>	10
<i>Anthonomus quadrigibbus</i>	12
<i>Anthonomus signatus</i>	11
<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	9
Apple fruit crinkle viroid	5
Apple necrotic mosaic virus	5
<i>Apriona cinerea</i>	8
<i>Apriona germari</i>	8
<i>Apriona rugicollis</i>	8
<i>Arrhenodes minutus</i>	8
<i>Aschistonyx eppoi</i> Inouye	6
Beet curly top virus	5
Black raspberry latent virus	7
Blueberry leaf mottle virus	7
<i>Botryosphaeria kuwatsukai</i>	11
Buckland valley grapevine yellows phytoplasma	5
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma americanum</i>	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma aurantifolia</i> -reference strain	6

Pest	Spread score
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma aurantifolia</i> –related strains (GD32; St_JO_10, 14, 17; PPT-SA; Rus-343F; PPT-GTO29, -GTO30, -SINTV; Potato Huayao Survey 2; Potato hair sprouts)	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma aurantifolia</i> -related strains (Pear decline Taiwan II, <i>Crotalaria witches' broom phytoplasma</i> , Sweet potato little leaf phytoplasma)	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma australiense</i> Davis et al. (reference strain)	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma cocostanzania</i> – subgroup16SrIV-C	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma fragariae</i> -related strains (YN-169, YN-10G)	5
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma fraxini</i> (reference strain)	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma hispanicum</i> (reference strain)	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma palmae</i> – subgroups 16SrIV-A, 16SrIV-B, 16SrIV-D, 16SrIV-E, 16SrIV-F	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma palmicola</i> – 16SrXXII-A	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma palmicola</i> -related strain 16SrXXII-B	6
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma phoenicium</i>	5
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma pruni</i> -related strain (North American grapevine yellows, NAGYIII)	10
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma pruni</i> -related strains (Clover yellow edge, Potato purple top Akpot7, MT117, Akpot6; PPT-COAHF, -GTOP)	10
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma pyri</i> -related strain (Peach yellow leaf roll)	10
Candidatus <i>Phytoplasma ziziphi</i> (reference strain)	5
<i>Carposina sasakii</i>	9
<i>Ceratocystis platani</i>	13
Cherry rasp leaf virus (CRLV)	12
Cherry rosette virus	12
Cherry rusty mottle associated virus	7
Cherry twisted leaf associated virus	7
<i>Choristoneura conflictana</i>	13
<i>Choristoneura fumiferana</i>	13
<i>Choristoneura parallela</i>	15
<i>Choristoneura rosaceana</i>	13
Chrysanthemum stem necrosis virus	10
<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	8
CiLV-C	10
CiLV-C2	10
CiLV-N sensu novo	10
Citrus strain of OFV	10
Citrus tristeza virus (non-EU isolates)	10
Coconut cadang-cadang viroid	7
<i>Coniferiporia sulphurascens</i>	11
<i>Coniferiporia weirii</i>	11
<i>Curtobacterium flaccumfaciens</i> pv. <i>Flaccumfaciens</i>	6
<i>Davidsoniella virescens</i>	9
<i>Diabrotica barberi</i>	4
<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	9
<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	9
<i>Diabrotica virgifera zea</i>	9

Pest	Spread score
<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	11
<i>Dimargarodes meridionalis</i>	6
<i>Elsinoë australis</i>	11
<i>Elsinoë fawcettii</i>	11
<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	9
<i>Eumargarodes laingi</i>	6
<i>Eurhizococcus brasiliensis</i>	6
<i>Eurhizococcus colombianus</i>	6
<i>Euwallacea fornicatus sensu lato</i>	8
<i>Exomala orientalis</i>	7
<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	18
<i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Albedinis</i>	11
<i>Geosmithia morbida</i>	12
<i>Globodera pallida</i>	10
<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	10
Grapevine berry inner necrosis virus	12
Grapevine red blotch virus	8
Grapevine vein-clearing virus	12
<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	8
<i>Grapholita packardi</i>	11
<i>Grapholita prunivora</i>	9
<i>Guignardia loricata</i>	8
<i>Helicoverpa zea</i>	13
HGSV-2	10
<i>Keiferia lycopersicella</i>	12
Lettuce infectious yellows virus	5
<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	9
<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	6
<i>Lycorma delicatula</i>	6
<i>Margarodes capensis</i>	6
<i>Margarodes greeni</i>	6
<i>Margarodes prieskaensis</i>	6
<i>Margarodes trimeni</i>	6
<i>Margarodes vitis</i>	6
<i>Margarodes vredendalensis</i>	6
<i>Massicus raddei</i>	8
<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	8
<i>Melampsora medusae f. sp. Tremuloidis</i>	8
<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	10
<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>	8
<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i> Karssen	10
<i>Mycodiella laricis-leptolepidis</i>	8
<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	8
<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	6

Pest	Spread score
<i>Nemorimyza maculosa</i>	9
<i>Neocosmospora ambrosia</i>	6
<i>Neocosmospora euwallaceae</i>	7
<i>Neoleucinodes elegantalis</i>	8
New Candidatus Phytoplasma causing palm lethal yellowing from 16SrIV group – ‘Bogia coconut syndrome’	6
<i>Oemona hirta</i>	12
<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	14
<i>Pantoea stewartii</i> subsp. <i>Stewartii</i>	6
Peach mosaic virus	8
Peach rosette mosaic virus	12
<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	10
<i>Phymatotrichopsis omnivora</i>	6
<i>Phyrdenus muriceus</i>	9
<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> (non-EU isolates)	16
<i>Pissodes nemorensis</i>	17
<i>Pissodes nitidus</i>	17
<i>Pissodes strobi</i>	17
<i>Pissodes terminalis</i>	17
<i>Pissodes yunnanensis</i>	17
<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>	17
Pomacea (Perry)	12
<i>Porphyrophora tritici</i>	6
Potato black ringspot virus	14
Potato virus H	14
Potato virus P	7
Potato virus T	11
Potato yellow dwarf virus	10
Potato yellow mosaic virus	10
Potato yellow vein virus	10
Potato yellowing virus	10
<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp.	9
<i>Prodiplosis longifila</i>	11
<i>Pseudocercospora angolensis</i>	10
<i>Pseudocercospora pini-densiflorae</i>	9
<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	11
<i>Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum</i>	11
<i>Ralstonia syzygii</i> subsp. <i>Celebesensis</i>	7
<i>Ralstonia syzygii</i> subsp. <i>Indonesiensis</i>	7
Raspberry latent virus	6
Raspberry leaf curl virus	6
<i>Rhigopsidius tucumanus</i>	9
<i>Rhynchophorus palmarum</i>	10
<i>Ripersiella hibisci</i>	7

Pest	Spread score
<i>Saperda candida</i>	8
Satsuma dwarf virus	6
<i>Scirtothrips aurantii</i>	9
<i>Scirtothrips citri</i>	11
<i>Scirtothrips dorsalis</i>	12
<i>Septoria malagutii</i>	9
<i>Sphaerulina musiva</i>	10
<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	10
<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	13
Squash vein yellowing virus	10
<i>Stagonosporopsis andigena</i>	9
<i>Stegophora ulmea</i>	8
Strawberry chlorotic fleck-associated virus	10
Strawberry leaf curl virus	10
Strawberry necrotic shock virus	5
<i>Tecia solanivora</i>	9
<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	13
Tobacco ringspot virus	12
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus	10
Tomato mosaic Havana virus	10
Tomato mottle Taino virus	10
Tomato ringspot virus	10
Tomato severe rugose virus	10
Tomato yellow vein streak virus	10
<i>Trirachys sartus</i>	8
<i>Unaspis citri</i>	11
<i>Venturia nashicola</i>	10
<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i> pv. <i>Oryzae</i>	6
<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i> pv. <i>Oryzicola</i>	6

Table 11: Host plants with an reported impact of the UQPs not considering spread scores (n=219)

<i>Abies balsamea</i>
<i>Abies</i> spp.
<i>Acer negundo</i>
<i>Acer saccharum</i>
<i>Actinidia</i> spp.
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>
<i>Allium cepa</i>
<i>Alnus rhombifolia</i>

<i>Amelanchier alnifolia</i>
<i>Anthoxanthum puelii</i>
<i>Apium graveolens</i>
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>
<i>Beta vulgaris</i>
<i>Beta vulgaris</i> subsp. <i>vulgaris</i>
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>botrytis</i>
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>capitata</i>
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>
<i>Castanea crenata</i>
<i>Castanea mollissima</i>
<i>Castanea sativa</i>
<i>Cedra</i> spp.
<i>Celtis sinensis</i>
<i>Chrysanthemum</i> spp.
<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>
<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>
<i>Citrus limon</i>
<i>Citrus limonia</i>
<i>Citrus reticulata</i>
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>
<i>Citrus</i> spp.
<i>Citrus unshiu</i>
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>
<i>Coniferus</i>
<i>Corylus avellana</i>
<i>Cucumis melo</i>
<i>Cucumis melo</i> var. <i>flexuosus</i>
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>
<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>
<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>
<i>Cuphea</i> spp.
<i>Cupressus</i> spp.
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>
<i>Daucus carota</i>
<i>Diospyros kaki</i>
<i>Dolichos</i> spp.
<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>
<i>Enkianthus perulatus</i>
<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>
<i>Fabaceae</i>
<i>Fagus crenata</i>
<i>Fagus</i> spp.

<i>Festuca rubra</i>
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>
<i>Fragaria</i> spp.
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>
<i>Fragaria virginiana</i>
<i>Glycine max</i>
<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i>
<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>
<i>Hibiscus</i> spp.
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>
<i>Juglans regia</i>
<i>Juglans nigra</i>
<i>Juniperus bonsai</i>
<i>Juniperus chinensis</i>
<i>Juniperus chinensis</i>
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>
<i>Larix decidua</i>
<i>Larix kaempferi</i>
<i>Larix laricina</i>
<i>Larix occidentalis</i>
<i>Larix</i> spp.
<i>Liriodendron</i> spp.
<i>Lolium</i> spp.
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>
<i>Malus baccata</i>
<i>Malus domestica</i>
<i>Malus prunifolia</i>
<i>Malus pumila</i>
<i>Malus sativa</i>
<i>Malus</i> sp.
<i>Malus</i> spp.
<i>Mangifera indica</i>
<i>Medicago sativa</i>
<i>Morus</i> spp.
<i>Nicotiana</i> spp.
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>
<i>Oryza sativa</i>
<i>Pelargonium</i> spp.
<i>Persea americana</i>
<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>
<i>Phleum pratense</i>
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>

<i>Phoenix</i> spp.
<i>Picea engelmannii</i>
<i>Picea pungens</i>
<i>Picea sitchensis</i>
<i>Picea</i> spp.
Pinaceae
<i>Pinus caribaea</i>
<i>Pinus contorta</i>
<i>Pinus densiflora</i>
<i>Pinus elliotii</i>
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>
<i>Pinus koraiensis</i>
<i>Pinus luchuensis</i>
<i>Pinus merkusii</i>
<i>Pinus muricata</i>
<i>Pinus nigra</i>
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>
<i>Pinus pinea</i>
<i>Pinus radiata</i>
<i>Pinus</i> spp.
<i>Pinus strobus</i>
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>
<i>Pinus thunbergii</i>
<i>Platanus acerifolia</i>
<i>Platanus orientalis</i>
<i>Platanus racemosa</i>
<i>Platanus</i> spp.
<i>Poncirus trifoliata</i>
<i>Populus tremuloides</i>
<i>Populus</i> × <i>canadensis</i>
<i>Populus alba</i>
<i>Populus deltoides</i>
<i>Populus euphratica</i>
<i>Populus nigra</i> × <i>maximowiczii</i>
<i>Populus</i> spp.
<i>Populus talassica</i>
<i>Populus tremuloides</i>
<i>Populus</i> × <i>euroamericana</i>
<i>Prunus dulcis</i>
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>
<i>Prunus avium</i>
<i>Prunus cerasus</i>
<i>Prunus domestica</i>
<i>Prunus dulcis</i>
<i>Prunus persica</i>
<i>Prunus persica</i>

<i>Prunus persica</i> var. <i>nucipersica</i>
<i>Prunus salicina</i>
<i>Prunus salicina</i> x <i>simonii</i>
<i>Prunus</i> sp.
<i>Prunus</i> spp.
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>
<i>Psidium guajava</i>
<i>Punica granatum</i>
<i>Pyrus bretschneideri</i>
<i>Pyrus communis</i>
<i>Pyrus pyrifolia</i> var. <i>culta</i>
<i>Pyrus ussuriensis</i>
<i>Pyrus</i> sp.
<i>Pyrus</i> spp.
<i>Quercus acuta</i>
<i>Quercus acutissima</i>
<i>Quercus aliena</i>
<i>Quercus dentata</i>
<i>Quercus liaotungensis</i>
<i>Quercus mongolica</i>
<i>Quercus robur</i>
<i>Quercus robur</i> subsp. <i>pedunculiflora</i>
<i>Quercus serrata</i>
<i>Quercus</i> sp.
<i>Quercus</i> spp.
<i>Quercus variabilis</i>
<i>Ricinus communis</i>
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>
<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i>
<i>Rosa</i> spp.
<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>
<i>Rubus</i> sp.
<i>Rubus</i> spp.
<i>Salix acmophylla</i>
<i>Salix aongarica</i>
<i>Salix laevigata</i>
<i>Salix miyabeana</i>
<i>Salix turanica</i>
<i>Scorzonera hispanica</i>
<i>Serissa</i> spp.
<i>Solanum betaceum</i>
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>
<i>Solanum melongena</i>
<i>Solanum quitoense</i>
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>

<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>
<i>Theobroma cacao</i>
<i>Thuja</i> spp.
<i>Trifolium repens</i>
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>
<i>Tsuga canadensis</i>
<i>Tsuga heterophylla</i>
Turf grasses
<i>Ulex europaeus</i>
<i>Ulmus glabra</i>
<i>Ulmus laevis</i>
<i>Ulmus minor</i>
<i>Ulmus pumila</i>
<i>Ulmus</i> spp.
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>
<i>Vaccinium</i> sp.
<i>Vigna</i> spp.
<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>
<i>Vitis labrusca</i> cv. <i>Concord</i>
<i>Vitis</i> spp.
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>
<i>Zea mays</i>
<i>Zea mays</i> convar. <i>Saccharata</i>
<i>Zelkova serrata</i>
<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i>

3 Conclusion

The European Commission (EC) requested EFSA to support the JRC, in shortlisting the UQPs and related host plants in the context of the review of the EC list of quarantine priority pests. The support of EFSA consisted essentially in the provision of scientifically sound data on pest host plants, and the identification of the pest spread mechanisms with the main objective of the Task B of this mandate to support the JRC in identifying not more than 30 new pests in addition to the 28 candidate priority pests assessed in 2019.

EFSA provides scientifically sound data that were systematically extracted for each pest primarily from the different EFSA outputs, pest risk analysis from other organization and scientific literature. The focus was on spread and impact data. Five criteria were used to reduce as much as possible the pest-host combinations not relevant for further analysis by JRC. One main criterion is the selection of pests able to cause damage to the crops based on observations on impact reported from the literature. Another main criterion is the estimation of a minimum spread score per pest, a simplified score specifically designed by EFSA for this prioritisation exercise.

Three different scenarios considering criteria one to five and different minimum spread scores (0, 7 to 11) are presented in the report.

In a first scenario, 57 UQPs pests with a minimum spread score of 11 are identified corresponding to 125 pest-host combinations and 84 host plants with reported observed impact for further analysis of the economic and environmental impacts. This minimum spread score would include all candidate priority pests assessed in 2019, ensuring consistency and continuity with the previous mandate.

The scenario where criterion 5 “spread score” is not used to filter out pest-host combinations results in 189 UQPs corresponding to 445 pest-host combinations and 219 host plants with an observed impact. These pests with their hosts are the ones on which further analysis is performed by the JRC of Sevilla for ranking the pests, considering their spread score as well as the economic data of the related hosts plants i.e. estimation of the value of production and area at risk (Cf. related JRC report).

Following the ranking of the UQPs by the JRC, in 2024, EFSA will perform fully fledged Expert Knowledge Elicitation (EKE) on spread and impact on a shortlist of maximum 30 pests as requested in the Task C of the current mandate and will update the EKEs on the 28 candidate priority pests assessed in 2019.

4 Annexes

Annex 1: List of pest-host combinations linked to the 57 UQPs retained with a minimum spread score of 11 (see Table 6)

Annex 2: List of pest-host combinations linked to the 143 UQPs retained with a minimum spread score of 7 (see Table 8)

Annex 3: List of pest-host combinations linked to the 189 UQPs retained without considering spread scores (see Table 10)

Annex 1: List of pest-host combinations linked to the 57 candidate priority pests with a minimum spread score of 11 (see Table 6)

Pest-Host Combinations	Spread score
Acleris gloverana	13
Tsuga heterophylla	13
Acleris issikii	13
Salix miyabeana	13
Acleris minuta	15
Malus sp.	15
Prunus sp.	15
Pyrus sp.	15
Acleris nishidai	13
Rubus sp.	13
Acleris semipurpurana	13
Quercus sp.	13
Acleris variana	13
Coniferus	13
Aleurocanthus citriperdus	11
Citrus spp.	11
Aleurocanthus spiniferus (Quaintance)	11
Citrus spp.	11
Rosa spp.	11
Aleurocanthus woglumi	11
Citrus spp.	11
Andean potato latent virus	16
Solanum tuberosum	16
Anthonomus bisignifer	11
Fragaria ananassa	11
Anthonomus quadrigibbus Say	12
Amelanchier alnifolia	12
Malus domestica	12
Prunus cerasus	12
Pyrus communis	12
Anthonomus signatus Say	11
Fragaria ananassa	11
Botryosphaeria kuwatsukai	11
Malus spp.	11
Pyrus spp.	11
Ceratocystis platani (J. M. Walter) Engelbr. & T. C. Harr	13
Platanus orientalis	13
Platanus spp.	13
Cherry rasp leaf virus (CRLV)	12
Malus domestica	12
Prunus avium	12
Prunus persica	12
Cherry rosette virus	12

Prunus avium	12
Choristoneura conflictana Walker	13
Populus tremuloides	13
Choristoneura fumiferana Clemens	13
Abies balsamea	13
Choristoneura parallela Robinson	15
Vaccinium sp.	15
Choristoneura rosaceana Harris	13
Prunus avium	13
Coniferiporia sulphurascens	11
Pseudotsuga menziesii	11
Coniferiporia weirii	11
Cupressus spp.	11
Thuja spp.	11
Diaphorina citri Kuwayana	11
Citrus spp.	11
Elsinoë australis	11
Citrus reticulata	11
Citrus sinensis	11
Elsinoë fawcettii	11
Citrus limonia	11
Poncirus trifoliata	11
Fusarium circinatum Nirenberg & O'Donnell	18
Pinus elliottii	18
Pinus halepensis	18
Pinus luchuensis	18
Pinus muricata	18
Pinus pinaster	18
Pinus pinea	18
Pinus radiata	18
Pseudotsuga menziesii	18
Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Albedinis	11
Phoenix dactylifera	11
Geosmithia morbida Kolarík, Freeland, Utley & Tisserat	12
Juglans regia	12
Juglans nigra	12
Grapevine berry inner necrosis virus	12
Vitis spp.	12
Grapevine vein-clearing virus	12
Vitis spp.	12
Grapholita packardi Zeller	11
Vaccinium corymbosum	11
Helicoverpa zea (Boddie)	13
Glycine max	13
Gossypium spp.	13
Solanum lycopersicum	13
Sorghum bicolor	13

Zea mays convar. Saccharata	13
Keiferia lycopersicella (Walsingham)	12
Solanum lycopersicum	12
Solanum melongena	12
Solanum tuberosum	12
Oeona hirta (Fabricius)	12
Citrus limon	12
Citrus reticulata	12
Citrus sinensis	12
Diospyros kaki	12
Malus domestica	12
Populus spp.	12
Ulex europaeus	12
Vitis vinifera	12
Oligonychus perditus Pritchard and Baker	14
Juniperus bonsai	14
Juniperus chinensis	14
Peach rosette mosaic virus	12
Prunus domestica	12
Prunus persica	12
Prunus salicina x simonii	12
Vaccinium corymbosum	12
Vitis spp.	12
Phytophthora ramorum (non-EU isolates)	16
Larix kaempferi	16
Pissodes nemorensis Germar	17
Cedra spp.	17
Picea spp.	17
Pinus spp.	17
Pissodes nitidus Roelofs	17
Pinus koraiensis	17
Pissodes strobi (Peck)	17
Picea sitchensis	17
Pinus strobus	17
Pissodes terminalis Hopping	17
Pinus contorta	17
Pissodes yunnanensis Langor & Zhang	17
Pinaceae	17
Polygraphus proximus Blandford	17
Abies spp.	17
Pomacea (Perry)	12
Oryza sativa	12
Potato black ringspot virus	14
Solanum tuberosum	14
Potato virus H	14
Solanum tuberosum	14
Potato virus T	11

Solanum tuberosum	11
Prodiplosis longifila Gagné	11
Asparagus officinalis	11
Capsicum annuum	11
Capsicum frutescens	11
Citrus aurantifolia	11
Gossypium spp.	11
Solanum lycopersicum	11
Solanum tuberosum	11
Puccinia pittieriana	11
Solanum tuberosum	11
Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum	11
Solanum lycopersicum	11
Solanum tuberosum	11
Scirtothrips citri (Moulton)	11
Citrus spp.	11
Vaccinium corymbosum	11
Scirtothrips dorsalis Hood	12
Camellia sinensis	12
Capsicum annuum	12
Citrus spp.	12
Gossypium herbaceum	12
Mangifera indica	12
Rosa rubiginosa	12
Vitis vinifera	12
Spodoptera litura (Fabricus)	13
Arachis hypogaea	13
Brassica oleracea var. botrytis	13
Brassica oleracea var. capitata	13
Capsicum annuum	13
Glycine max	13
Gossypium spp.	13
Nicotiana spp.	13
Solanum lycopersicum	13
Solanum melongena	13
Zea mays	13
Thecaphora solani	13
Solanum tuberosum	13
Tobacco ringspot virus	12
Glycine max	12
Nicotiana tabacum	12
Vaccinium corymbosum	12
Vitis vinifera	12
Unaspis citri (Comstock)	11
Citrus spp.	11

Annex 2: List of pest-host combinations linked to the 143 UQPs with a minimum spread score of 7 (see Table 8)

Pest-host combinations	Spread score
Acleris gloverana	13
Tsuga heterophylla	13
Acleris issikii	13
Salix miyabeana	13
Acleris minuta	15
Malus sp.	15
Prunus sp.	15
Pyrus sp.	15
Acleris nishidai	13
Rubus sp.	13
Acleris semipurpurana	13
Quercus sp.	13
Acleris variana	13
Coniferus	13
Acrobasis pyrivorella	8
Pyrus spp.	8
Aleurocanthus citriperdus	11
Citrus spp.	11
Aleurocanthus spiniferus (Quaintance)	11
Citrus spp.	11
Rosa spp.	11
Aleurocanthus woglumi	11
Citrus spp.	11
Andean potato latent virus	16
Solanum tuberosum	16
Andean potato mottle virus	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Anisogramma anomala	9
Corylus avellana	9
Anthonomus bisignifer	11
Fragaria ananassa	11
Anthonomus grandis (Boh.)	10
Gossypium spp.	10
Hibiscus spp.	10
Anthonomus quadrigibbus Say	12
Amelanchier alnifolia	12
Malus domestica	12
Prunus cerasus	12
Pyrus communis	12
Anthonomus signatus Say	11
Fragaria ananassa	11
Apiosporina morbosa	9

Prunus cerasus	9
Prunus domestica	9
Apriona cinerea Chevrolat	8
Malus domestica	8
Populus spp.	8
Apriona germari (Hope)	8
Morus spp.	8
Populus spp.	8
Apriona rugicollis Chevrolat	8
Celtis sinensis	8
Enkianthus perulatus	8
Fagus crenata	8
Morus spp.	8
Robinia pseudoacacia	8
Zelkova serrata	8
Arrhenodes minutus Drury	8
Fagus spp.	8
Populus spp.	8
Quercus spp.	8
Ulmus spp.	8
Black raspberry latent virus	7
Fragaria ananassa	7
Blueberry leaf mottle virus	7
Vaccinium corymbosum	7
Vitis labrusca cv. Concord	7
Vitis vinifera	7
Botryosphaeria kuwatsukai	11
Malus spp.	11
Pyrus spp.	11
Candidatus Phytoplasma pruni-related strain (North American grapevine yellows, NAGYIII) Davis et al.	10
Vitis vinifera	10
Candidatus Phytoplasma pruni-related strains (Clover yellow edge, Potato purple top Akpot7, MT117, Akpot6; PPT-COHP, -GTOP)	10
Solanum lycopersicum	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Candidatus Phytoplasma pyri-related strain (Peach yellow leaf roll) Norton et al.	10
Prunus persica	10
Carposina sasakii Matsumara	9
Malus domestica	9
Prunus domestica	9
Prunus persica	9
Pyrus communis	9
Ziziphus jujuba	9
Ceratocystis platani (J. M. Walter) Engelbr. & T. C. Harr	13
Platanus orientalis	13
Platanus spp.	13
Cherry rasp leaf virus (CRLV)	12

Malus domestica	12
Prunus avium	12
Prunus persica	12
Cherry rosette virus	12
Prunus avium	12
Cherry rusty mottle associated virus	7
Prunus avium	7
Cherry twisted leaf associated virus	7
Prunus spp.	7
Choristoneura conflictana Walker	13
Populus tremuloides	13
Choristoneura fumiferana Clemens	13
Abies balsamea	13
Choristoneura parallela Robinson	15
Vaccinium sp.	15
Choristoneura rosaceana Harris	13
Prunus avium	13
Chrysanthemum stem necrosis virus	10
Chrysanthemum spp.	10
Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli	8
Picea engelmannii	8
Picea pungens	8
CiLV-C	10
Citrus sinensis	10
CiLV-C2	10
Citrus sinensis	10
CiLV-N sensu novo	10
Citrus sinensis	10
Citrus strain of OFV	10
Citrus sinensis	10
Citrus tristeza virus (non-EU isolates)	10
Citrus reticulata	10
Citrus sinensis	10
Coconut cadang-cadang viroid	7
Cocos nucifera	7
Coniferiporia sulphurascens	11
Pseudotsuga menziesii	11
Coniferiporia weirii	11
Cupressus spp.	11
Thuja spp.	11
Davidsoniella virescens	9
Acer saccharum	9
Liriodendron spp.	9
Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi Barber	9
Arachis hypogaea	9
Cucurbitaceae	9
Fabaceae	9

Zea mays	9
Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata Mannerheim	9
Cucumis melo	9
Cucurbitaceae	9
Diabrotica virgifera zae Kryan & Smith	9
Zea mays	9
Diaphorina citri Kuwayana	11
Citrus spp.	11
Elsinoë australis	11
Citrus reticulata	11
Citrus sinensis	11
Elsinoë fawcettii	11
Citrus limonia	11
Poncirus trifoliata	11
Eotetranychus lewisi (McGregor)	9
Citrus limon	9
Citrus sinensis	9
Euphorbia pulcherrima	9
Fragaria ananassa	9
Prunus persica	9
Rubus idaeus	9
Euwallacea fornicatus sensu lato	8
Acer negundo	8
Alnus rhombifolia	8
Camellia sinensis	8
Citrus spp.	8
Persea americana	8
Platanus racemosa	8
Punica granatum	8
Quercus robur	8
Quercus robur subsp. pedunculiflora	8
Ricinus communis	8
Salix laevigata	8
Theobroma cacao	8
Exomala orientalis (Waterhouse)	7
Turf grasses	7
Vaccinium corymbosum	7
Vaccinium myrtillus	7
Zea mays	7
Fusarium circinatum Nirenberg & O'Donnell	18
Pinus elliotii	18
Pinus halepensis	18
Pinus luchuensis	18
Pinus muricata	18
Pinus pinaster	18
Pinus pinea	18
Pinus radiata	18

Pseudotsuga menziesii	18
Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Albedinis	11
Phoenix dactylifera	11
Geosmithia morbida Kolarík, Freeland, Utley & Tisserat	12
Juglans regia	12
Juglans nigra	12
Globodera pallida (Stone) Behrens	10
Solanum lycopersicum	10
Solanum melongena	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Globodera rostochiensis (Wollenweber) Behrens	10
Solanum lycopersicum	10
Solanum melongena	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Grapevine berry inner necrosis virus	12
Vitis spp.	12
Grapevine red blotch virus	8
Vitis spp.	8
Grapevine vein-clearing virus	12
Vitis spp.	12
Grapholita inopinata (Heinrich)	8
Malus baccata	8
Malus domestica	8
Malus prunifolia	8
Grapholita packardi Zeller	11
Vaccinium corymbosum	11
Grapholita prunivora (Walsh)	9
Malus domestica	9
Guignardia loricata	8
Larix decidua	8
Larix laricina	8
Larix occidentalis	8
Helicoverpa zea (Boddie)	13
Glycine max	13
Gossypium spp.	13
Solanum lycopersicum	13
Sorghum bicolor	13
Zea mays convar. Saccharata	13
HGSV-2	10
Citrus sinensis	10
Keiferia lycopersicella (Walsingham)	12
Solanum lycopersicum	12
Solanum melongena	12
Solanum tuberosum	12
Liriomyza sativae Blanchard	9
Apium graveolens	9
Medicago sativa	9

Massicus raddei (Blessig)	8
Castanea crenata	8
Castanea mollissima	8
Castanea sativa	8
Quercus acuta	8
Quercus acutissima	8
Quercus aliena	8
Quercus dentata	8
Quercus liaotungensis	8
Quercus mongolica	8
Quercus serrata	8
Quercus variabilis	8
Melampsora farlowii	8
Tsuga canadensis	8
Melampsora medusae f. sp. Tremuloidis	8
Populus tremuloides	8
Meloidogyne chitwoodi Golden et al.	10
Daucus carota	10
Scorzonera hispanica	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Meloidogyne enterolobii Yang & Eisenback	8
Capsicum annuum	8
Citrullus lanatus	8
Cucumis sativus	8
Glycine max	8
Gossypium spp.	8
Ipomoea batatas	8
Psidium guajava	8
Solanum lycopersicum	8
Vigna unguiculata	8
Meloidogyne fallax Karssen	10
Daucus carota	10
Scorzonera hispanica	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Mycodiella laricis-leptolepidis	8
Larix spp.	8
Nacobbus aberrans (Thorne) Thorne and Allen	8
Beta vulgaris subsp vulgaris	8
Phaseolus vulgaris	8
Solanum lycopersicum	8
Solanum tuberosum	8
Nemorimyza maculosa (Malloch)	9
Chrysanthemum spp.	9
Lactuca sativa	9
Neocosmospora euwallaceae	7
Persea americana	7
Neoleucinodes elegantalis (Guenée)	8

Capsicum annuum	8
Solanum betaceum	8
Solanum lycopersicum	8
Solanum melongena	8
Solanum quitoense	8
Oeonia hirta (Fabricius)	12
Citrus limon	12
Citrus reticulata	12
Citrus sinensis	12
Diospyros kaki	12
Malus domestica	12
Populus spp.	12
Ulex europaeus	12
Vitis vinifera	12
Oligonychus perditus Pritchard and Baker	14
Juniperus bonsai	14
Juniperus chinensis	14
Peach mosaic virus	8
Prunus armeniaca	8
Prunus domestica	8
Prunus persica	8
Prunus salicina	8
Peach rosette mosaic virus	12
Prunus domestica	12
Prunus persica	12
Prunus salicina x simonii	12
Vaccinium corymbosum	12
Vitis spp.	12
Phyllosticta solitaria	10
Malus domestica	10
Phyrdenus muriceus	9
Solanum lycopersicum	9
Solanum melongena	9
Solanum tuberosum	9
Phytophthora ramorum (non-EU isolates)	16
Larix kaempferi	16
Pissodes nemorensis Germar	17
Cedra spp.	17
Picea spp.	17
Pinus spp.	17
Pissodes nitidus Roelofs	17
Pinus koraiensis	17
Pissodes strobi (Peck)	17
Picea sitchensis	17
Pinus strobus	17
Pissodes terminalis Hopping	17
Pinus contorta	17

Pissodes yunnanensis Langor & Zhang	17
Pinaceae	17
Polygraphus proximus Blandford	17
Abies spp.	17
Pomacea (Perry)	12
Oryza sativa	12
Potato black ringspot virus	14
Solanum tuberosum	14
Potato virus H	14
Solanum tuberosum	14
Potato virus P	7
Solanum tuberosum	7
Potato virus T	11
Solanum tuberosum	11
Potato yellow dwarf virus	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Potato yellow mosaic virus	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Potato yellow vein virus	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Potato yellowing virus	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Premnotrypes spp.	9
Solanum tuberosum	9
Prodiplosis longifila Gagné	11
Asparagus officinalis	11
Capsicum annuum	11
Capsicum frutescens	11
Citrus aurantifolia	11
Gossypium spp.	11
Solanum lycopersicum	11
Solanum tuberosum	11
Pseudocercospora angolensis	10
Citrus spp.	10
Pseudocercospora pini-densiflorae	9
Pinus caribaea	9
Pinus densiflora	9
Pinus halepensis	9
Pinus merkusii	9
Pinus nigra	9
Pinus pinaster	9
Pinus pinea	9
Pinus radiata	9
Pinus sylvestris	9
Pinus thunbergii	9
Puccinia pittieriana	11
Solanum tuberosum	11

Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum	11
Solanum lycopersicum	11
Solanum tuberosum	11
Ralstonia syzygii subsp. Celebesensis	7
Solanum lycopersicum	7
Solanum tuberosum	7
Ralstonia syzygii subsp. Indonesiensis	7
Solanum lycopersicum	7
Solanum tuberosum	7
Rhigopsidius tucumanus	9
Solanum tuberosum	9
Rhynchophorus palmarum (L.)	10
Cocos nucifera	10
Elaeis guineensis	10
Ripersiella hibisci Kawai and Takagi	7
Cuphea spp.	7
Hibiscus spp.	7
Pelargonium spp.	7
Phoenix spp.	7
Serissa spp.	7
Saperda candida Fabricius	8
Malus domestica	8
Scirtothrips aurantii Faure	9
Citrus sinensis	9
Mangifera indica	9
Scirtothrips citri (Moulton)	11
Citrus spp.	11
Vaccinium corymbosum	11
Scirtothrips dorsalis Hood	12
Camellia sinensis	12
Capsicum annuum	12
Citrus spp.	12
Gossypium herbaceum	12
Mangifera indica	12
Rosa rubiginosa	12
Vitis vinifera	12
Septoria malagutii	9
Solanum tuberosum	9
Sphaerulina musiva	10
Populus × canadensis	10
Populus deltoides	10
Populus nigra x maximowiczii	10
Spodoptera eridania (Cramer)	10
Helianthus annuus	10
Ipomoea batatas	10
Solanum lycopersicum	10
Spodoptera litura (Fabricus)	13

Arachis hypogaea	13
Brassica oleracea var. botrytis	13
Brassica oleracea var. capitata	13
Capsicum annuum	13
Glycine max	13
Gossypium spp.	13
Nicotiana spp.	13
Solanum lycopersicum	13
Solanum melongena	13
Zea mays	13
Squash vein yellowing virus	10
Citrullus lanatus	10
Cucurbita pepo	10
Stagonosporopsis andigena	9
Solanum tuberosum	9
Stegophora ulmea	8
Ulmus glabra	8
Ulmus laevis	8
Strawberry chlorotic fleck-associated virus	10
Fragaria vesca	10
Fragaria virginiana	10
Strawberry leaf curl virus	10
Fragaria spp.	10
Tecia solanivora (Povolný)	9
Solanum tuberosum	9
Thecaphora solani	13
Solanum tuberosum	13
Tobacco ringspot virus	12
Glycine max	12
Nicotiana tabacum	12
Vaccinium corymbosum	12
Vitis vinifera	12
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus	10
Capsicum annuum	10
Capsicum frutescens	10
Chrysanthemum spp.	10
Cucumis melo	10
Cucumis melo var. flexuosus	10
Cucumis sativus	10
Cucurbita pepo	10
Gossypium hirsutum	10
Luffa cylindrica	10
Solanum lycopersicum	10
Solanum melongena	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Tomato mosaic Havana virus	10
Solanum lycopersicum	10

Tomato mottle Taino virus	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Tomato ringspot virus	10
Malus domestica	10
Prunus domestica	10
Prunus dulcis	10
Prunus persica	10
Rubus idaeus	10
Vitis vinifera	10
Tomato severe rugose virus	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Tomato yellow vein streak virus	10
Solanum lycopersicum	10
Solanum tuberosum	10
Trirachys sartus (Solsky)	8
Juglans regia	8
Malus domestica	8
Malus pumila	8
Platanus acerifolia	8
Platanus orientalis	8
Populus alba	8
Populus euphratica	8
Populus talassica	8
Populus x euroamericana	8
Salix acmophylla	8
Salix aongarica	8
Salix turanica	8
Ulmus minor	8
Ulmus pumila	8
Unaspis citri (Comstock)	11
Citrus spp.	11
Venturia nashicola	10
Pyrus bretschneideri	10
Pyrus pyrifolia var.culta	10
Pyrus ussuriensis	10

Annex 3: List of pest-host combinations linked to the 189 UQPs without considering spread scores (see Table 10)

Acleris gloverana	13
<i>Tsuga heterophylla</i>	13
Acleris issikii	13
<i>Salix miyabeana</i>	13
Acleris minuta	15
<i>Malus</i> sp.	15
<i>Prunus</i> sp.	15
<i>Pyrus</i> sp.	15
Acleris nishidai	13
<i>Rubus</i> sp.	13
Acleris semipurpurana	13
<i>Quercus</i> sp.	13
Acleris variana	13
<i>Coniferus</i>	13
Acrobasis pyrivorella	8
<i>Pyrus</i> spp.	8
Aleurocanthus citriperdus	11
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	11
Aleurocanthus spiniferus (Quaintance)	11
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	11
<i>Rosa</i> spp.	11
Aleurocanthus woglumi	11
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	11
Andean potato latent virus	16
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	16
Andean potato mottle virus	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Anisogramma anomala	9
<i>Corylus avellana</i>	9
Anthonomus bisignifer	11
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>	11
Anthonomus grandis (Boh.)	10
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.	10
<i>Hibiscus</i> spp.	10
Anthonomus quadrigibbus Say	12
<i>Amelanchier alnifolia</i>	12
<i>Malus domestica</i>	12
<i>Prunus cerasus</i>	12
<i>Pyrus communis</i>	12
Anthonomus signatus Say	11
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>	11
Apiosporina morbosa	9
<i>Prunus cerasus</i>	9
<i>Prunus domestica</i>	9

Apple fruit crinkle viroid	5
<i>Malus domestica</i>	5
Apple necrotic mosaic virus	5
<i>Malus domestica</i>	5
Apriona cinerea Chevrolat	8
<i>Malus domestica</i>	8
<i>Populus</i> spp.	8
Apriona germari (Hope)	8
<i>Morus</i> spp.	8
<i>Populus</i> spp.	8
Apriona rugicollis Chevrolat	8
<i>Celtis sinensis</i>	8
<i>Enkianthus perulatus</i>	8
<i>Fagus crenata</i>	8
<i>Morus</i> spp.	8
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	8
<i>Zelkova serrata</i>	8
Arrhenodes minutus Drury	8
<i>Fagus</i> spp.	8
<i>Populus</i> spp.	8
<i>Quercus</i> spp.	8
<i>Ulmus</i> spp.	8
Aschistonyx eppoi Inouye	6
<i>Juniperus chinensis</i>	6
Beet curly top virus	5
<i>Beta vulgaris</i>	5
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	5
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	5
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	5
Black raspberry latent virus	7
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>	7
Blueberry leaf mottle virus	7
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	7
<i>Vitis labrusca</i> cv. Concord	7
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	7
Botryosphaeria kuwatsukai	11
<i>Malus</i> spp.	11
<i>Pyrus</i> spp.	11
Buckland valley grapevine yellows phytoplasma	5
<i>Vitis</i> spp.	5
Candidatus Phytoplasma americanum	6
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma aurantifolia-reference strain	6
<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma aurantifolia-related strains (GD32; St_JO_10, 14, 17; PPT-SA; Rus-343F; PPT-GTO29, -GTO30, -SINTV; Potato Huayao Survey 2; Potato hair sprouts)	6
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	6

Candidatus Phytoplasma aurantifolia-related strains (Pear decline Taiwan II, Crotalaria witches' broom phytoplasma, Sweet potato little leaf phytoplasma)	6
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma australiense Davis et al. (reference strain)	6
<i>Fragaria</i> spp.	6
<i>Prunus</i> spp.	6
<i>Rubus</i> spp.	6
<i>Vitis</i> spp.	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma cocostanzania – subgroup 16SrIV-C	6
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma fragariae-related strains (YN-169, YN-10G)	5
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	5
Candidatus Phytoplasma fraxini (reference strain) Griffiths et al.	6
<i>Fragaria</i> spp.	6
<i>Prunus</i> spp.	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma hispanicum (reference strain) Davis et al.	6
<i>Fragaria</i> spp.	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma palmae – subgroups 16SrIV-A, 16SrIV-B, 16SrIV-D, 16SrIV-E, 16SrIV-F	6
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma palmicola – 16SrXXII-A	6
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma palmicola-related strain 16SrXXII-B	6
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	6
Candidatus Phytoplasma phoenicium	5
<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	5
<i>Prunus persica</i>	5
<i>Prunus persica</i> var. <i>nucipersica</i>	5
Candidatus Phytoplasma pruni-related strain (North American grapevine yellows, NAGYIII) Davis et al.	10
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	10
Candidatus Phytoplasma pruni-related strains (Clover yellow edge, Potato purple top Akpot7, MT117, Akpot6; PPT-COHP, -GTOP)	10
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Candidatus Phytoplasma pyri-related strain (Peach yellow leaf roll) Norton et al.	10
<i>Prunus persica</i>	10
Candidatus Phytoplasma ziziphi (reference strain) Jung et al.	5
<i>Malus domestica</i>	5
<i>Prunus avium</i>	5
<i>Prunus persica</i>	5
Carposina sasakii Matsumara	9
<i>Malus domestica</i>	9
<i>Prunus domestica</i>	9
<i>Prunus persica</i>	9
<i>Pyrus communis</i>	9
<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i>	9

Ceratocystis platani (J. M. Walter) Engelbr. & T. C. Harr	13
<i>Platanus orientalis</i>	13
<i>Platanus</i> spp.	13
Cherry rasp leaf virus (CRLV)	12
<i>Malus domestica</i>	12
<i>Prunus avium</i>	12
<i>Prunus persica</i>	12
Cherry rosette virus	12
<i>Prunus avium</i>	12
Cherry rusty mottle associated virus	7
<i>Prunus avium</i>	7
Cherry twisted leaf associated virus	7
<i>Prunus</i> spp.	7
Choristoneura conflictana Walker	13
<i>Populus tremuloides</i>	13
Choristoneura fumiferana Clemens	13
<i>Abies balsamea</i>	13
Choristoneura parallela Robinson	15
<i>Vaccinium</i> sp.	15
Choristoneura rosaceana Harris	13
<i>Prunus avium</i>	13
Chrysanthemum stem necrosis virus	10
<i>Chrysanthemum</i> spp.	10
Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli	8
<i>Picea engelmannii</i>	8
<i>Picea pungens</i>	8
CiLV-C	10
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	10
CiLV-C2	10
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	10
CiLV-N sensu novo	10
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	10
Citrus strain of OFV	10
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	10
Citrus tristeza virus (non-EU isolates)	10
<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	10
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	10
Coconut cadang-cadang viroid	7
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	7
Coniferiporia sulphurascens	11
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	11
Coniferiporia weirii	11
<i>Cupressus</i> spp.	11
<i>Thuja</i> spp.	11
Curtobacterium flaccumfaciens pv. Flaccumfaciens	6
<i>Dolichos</i> spp.	6
<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	6

<i>Vigna</i> spp.	6
Davidsoniella virescens	9
<i>Acer saccharum</i>	9
<i>Liriodendron</i> spp.	9
Diabrotica barberi Smith and Lawrence	4
<i>Zea mays</i>	4
Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi Barber	9
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	9
Cucurbitaceae	9
Fabaceae	9
<i>Zea mays</i>	9
Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata Mannerheim	9
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	9
Cucurbitaceae	9
Diabrotica virgifera zae Kryan & Smith	9
<i>Zea mays</i>	9
Diaphorina citri Kuwayana	11
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	11
Dimargarodes meridionalis Morrison	6
Turf grasses	6
Elsinoë australis	11
<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	11
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	11
Elsinoë fawcettii	11
<i>Citrus limonia</i>	11
<i>Poncirus trifoliata</i>	11
Eotetranychus lewisi (McGregor)	9
<i>Citrus limon</i>	9
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	9
<i>Euphorbia pulcherrima</i>	9
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>	9
<i>Prunus persica</i>	9
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	9
Eumargarodes laingi Allsopp et al.	6
Turf grasses	6
Eurhizococcus brasiliensis Jakubski	6
<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	6
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	6
<i>Vaccinium</i> sp.	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Eurhizococcus colombianus Jakubski	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Euwallacea fornicatus sensu lato	8
<i>Acer negundo</i>	8
<i>Alnus rhombifolia</i>	8
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	8
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	8

<i>Persea americana</i>	8
<i>Platanus racemosa</i>	8
<i>Punica granatum</i>	8
<i>Quercus robur</i>	8
<i>Quercus robur subsp. pedunculiflora</i>	8
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	8
<i>Salix laevigata</i>	8
<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	8
Exomala orientalis (Waterhouse)	7
<i>Turf grasses</i>	7
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	7
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	7
<i>Zea mays</i>	7
Fusarium circinatum Nirenberg & O'Donnell	18
<i>Pinus elliotii</i>	18
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	18
<i>Pinus luchuensis</i>	18
<i>Pinus muricata</i>	18
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	18
<i>Pinus pinea</i>	18
<i>Pinus radiata</i>	18
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	18
Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. Albedinis	11
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	11
Geosmithia morbida Kolarík, Freeland, Utley & Tisserat	12
<i>Juglans regia</i>	12
<i>Juglans nigra</i>	12
Globodera pallida (Stone) Behrens	10
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	10
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Globodera rostochiensis (Wollenweber) Behrens	10
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	10
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Grapevine berry inner necrosis virus	12
<i>Vitis</i> spp.	12
Grapevine red blotch virus	8
<i>Vitis</i> spp.	8
Grapevine vein-clearing virus	12
<i>Vitis</i> spp.	12
Grapholita inopinata (Heinrich)	8
<i>Malus baccata</i>	8
<i>Malus domestica</i>	8
<i>Malus prunifolia</i>	8
Grapholita packardi Zeller	11
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	11

Grapholita prunivora (Walsh)	9
<i>Malus domestica</i>	9
Guignardia loricata	8
<i>Larix decidua</i>	8
<i>Larix laricina</i>	8
<i>Larix occidentalis</i>	8
Helicoverpa zea (Boddie)	13
<i>Glycine max</i>	13
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.	13
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	13
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	13
<i>Zea mays</i> convar. <i>Saccharata</i>	13
HGSV-2	10
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	10
Keiferia lycopersicella (Walsingham)	12
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	12
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	12
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	12
Lettuce infectious yellows virus	5
<i>Beta vulgaris</i>	5
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	5
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	5
Liriomyza sativae Blanchard	9
<i>Apium graveolens</i>	9
<i>Medicago sativa</i>	9
Lissonotus bonariensis (Kuschel)	6
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	6
<i>Anthoxanthum puelii</i>	6
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	6
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	6
<i>Lolium</i> spp.	6
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	6
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	6
Lycorma delicatula (White)	6
<i>Actinidia</i> spp.	6
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>	6
<i>Malus</i> spp.	6
<i>Prunus</i> spp.	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Margarodes capensis Giard	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Margarodes greeni Brain	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Margarodes prieskaensis (Jakubski)	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Margarodes trimeni Brain	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6

Margarodes vitis Reed	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Margarodes vredendalensis de Klerk	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Massicus raddei (Blessig)	8
<i>Castanea crenata</i>	8
<i>Castanea mollissima</i>	8
<i>Castanea sativa</i>	8
<i>Quercus acuta</i>	8
<i>Quercus acutissima</i>	8
<i>Quercus aliena</i>	8
<i>Quercus dentata</i>	8
<i>Quercus liaotungensis</i>	8
<i>Quercus mongolica</i>	8
<i>Quercus serrata</i>	8
<i>Quercus variabilis</i>	8
Melampsora farlowii	8
<i>Tsuga canadensis</i>	8
Melampsora medusae f. sp. Tremuloidis	8
<i>Populus tremuloides</i>	8
Meloidogyne chitwoodi Golden et al.	10
<i>Daucus carota</i>	10
<i>Scorzonera hispanica</i>	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Meloidogyne enterolobii Yang & Eisenback	8
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	8
<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	8
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	8
<i>Glycine max</i>	8
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.	8
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	8
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	8
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	8
<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	8
Meloidogyne fallax Karszen	10
<i>Daucus carota</i>	10
<i>Scorzonera hispanica</i>	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Mycodiella laricis-leptolepidis	8
<i>Larix</i> spp.	8
Nacobbus aberrans (Thorne) Thorne and Allen	8
<i>Beta vulgaris</i> subsp <i>vulgaris</i>	8
<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	8
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	8
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	8
Naupactus leucoloma Boheman	6
<i>Allium cepa</i>	6

<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	6
<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>	6
<i>Glycine max</i>	6
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	6
<i>Medicago sativa</i>	6
<i>Prunus avium</i>	6
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	6
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	6
Nemorimyza maculosa (Malloch)	9
<i>Chrysanthemum</i> spp.	9
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	9
Neocosmospora ambrosia	6
<i>Persea americana</i>	6
Neocosmospora euwallaceae	7
<i>Persea americana</i>	7
Neoleucinodes elegantalis (Guenée)	8
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	8
<i>Solanum betaceum</i>	8
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	8
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	8
<i>Solanum quitoense</i>	8
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Oeona hirta (Fabricius)	12
<i>Citrus limon</i>	12
<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	12
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	12
<i>Diospyros kaki</i>	12
<i>Malus domestica</i>	12
<i>Populus</i> spp.	12
<i>Ulex europaeus</i>	12
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	12
Oligonychus perditus Pritchard and Baker	14
<i>Juniperus bonsai</i>	14
<i>Juniperus chinensis</i>	14
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<i>Oryza sativa</i>	6
<i>Zea mays</i> convar. <i>Saccharata</i>	6
Peach mosaic virus	8
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	8
<i>Prunus domestica</i>	8
<i>Prunus persica</i>	8
<i>Prunus salicina</i>	8
Peach rosette mosaic virus	12
<i>Prunus domestica</i>	12
<i>Prunus persica</i>	12
<i>Prunus salicina</i> x <i>simonii</i>	12

<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	12
<i>Vitis</i> spp.	12
Phyllosticta solitaria	10
<i>Malus domestica</i>	10
Phymatotrichopsis omnivora	6
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.	6
<i>Malus domestica</i>	6
<i>Malus sativa</i>	6
<i>Prunus persica</i>	6
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	6
Phyrdenus muriceus	9
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	9
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Phytophthora ramorum (non-EU isolates)	16
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Pissodes nemorensis Germar	17
<i>Cedra</i> spp.	17
<i>Picea</i> spp.	17
<i>Pinus</i> spp.	17
Pissodes nitidus Roelofs	17
<i>Pinus koraiensis</i>	17
Pissodes strobi (Peck)	17
<i>Picea sitchensis</i>	17
<i>Pinus strobus</i>	17
Pissodes terminalis Hopping	17
<i>Pinus contorta</i>	17
Pissodes yunnanensis Langor & Zhang	17
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Polygraphus proximus Blandford	17
<i>Abies</i> spp.	17
Pomacea (Perry)	12
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	12
Porphyrophora tritici Sarkisov et al.	6
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	6
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<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	14
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<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	14
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<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	7
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<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	11
Potato yellow dwarf virus	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Potato yellow mosaic virus	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10

Potato yellow vein virus	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Potato yellowing virus	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Premnotrypes spp.	9
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	9
Prodiplosis longifila Gagné	11
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	11
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	11
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	11
<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>	11
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.	11
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	11
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	11
Pseudocercospora angolensis	10
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	10
Pseudocercospora pini-densiflorae	9
<i>Pinus caribaea</i>	9
<i>Pinus densiflora</i>	9
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	9
<i>Pinus merkusii</i>	9
<i>Pinus nigra</i>	9
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	9
<i>Pinus pinea</i>	9
<i>Pinus radiata</i>	9
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	9
<i>Pinus thunbergii</i>	9
Puccinia pittieriana	11
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	11
Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum	11
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	11
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	11
Ralstonia syzygii subsp. Celebesensis	7
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	7
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	7
Ralstonia syzygii subsp. Indonesiensis	7
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	7
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	7
Raspberry latent virus	6
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	6
Raspberry leaf curl virus	6
<i>Rubus</i> spp.	6
Rhigopsidius tucumanus	9
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	9
Rhynchophorus palmarum (L.)	10
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	10
<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	10

Ripersiella hibisci Kawai and Takagi	7
<i>Cuphea</i> spp.	7
<i>Hibiscus</i> spp.	7
<i>Pelargonium</i> spp.	7
<i>Phoenix</i> spp.	7
<i>Serissa</i> spp.	7
Saperda candida Fabricius	8
<i>Malus domestica</i>	8
Satsuma dwarf virus	6
<i>Citrus unshiu</i>	6
Scirtothrips aurantii Faure	9
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	9
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	9
Scirtothrips citri (Moulton)	11
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	11
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	11
Scirtothrips dorsalis Hood	12
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	12
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	12
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	12
<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i>	12
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	12
<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i>	12
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	12
Septoria malagutii	9
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	9
Sphaerulina musiva	10
<i>Populus × canadensis</i>	10
<i>Populus deltoides</i>	10
<i>Populus nigra x maximowiczii</i>	10
Spodoptera eridania (Cramer)	10
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	10
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	10
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	10
Spodoptera litura (Fabricius)	13
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	13
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>botrytis</i>	13
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>capitata</i>	13
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	13
<i>Glycine max</i>	13
<i>Gossypium</i> spp.	13
<i>Nicotiana</i> spp.	13
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	13
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	13
<i>Zea mays</i>	13
Squash vein yellowing virus	10
<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	10

<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	10
Stagonosporopsis andigena	9
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	9
Stegophora ulmea	8
<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	8
<i>Ulmus laevis</i>	8
Strawberry chlorotic fleck-associated virus	10
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	10
<i>Fragaria virginiana</i>	10
Strawberry leaf curl virus	10
<i>Fragaria</i> spp.	10
Strawberry necrotic shock virus	5
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	5
<i>Rubus</i> spp.	5
Tecia solanivora (Povolný)	9
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	9
Thecaphora solani	13
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	13
Tobacco ringspot virus	12
<i>Glycine max</i>	12
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	12
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	12
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	12
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus	10
<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	10
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	10
<i>Chrysanthemum</i> spp.	10
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	10
<i>Cucumis melo var. flexuosus</i>	10
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	10
<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	10
<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	10
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>	10
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	10
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Tomato mosaic Havana virus	10
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	10
Tomato mottle Taino virus	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Tomato ringspot virus	10
<i>Malus domestica</i>	10
<i>Prunus domestica</i>	10
<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	10
<i>Prunus persica</i>	10
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	10
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	10

Tomato severe rugose virus	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Tomato yellow vein streak virus	10
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	10
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	10
Trirachys sartus (Solsky)	8
<i>Juglans regia</i>	8
<i>Malus domestica</i>	8
<i>Malus pumila</i>	8
<i>Platanus acerifolia</i>	8
<i>Platanus orientalis</i>	8
<i>Populus alba</i>	8
<i>Populus euphratica</i>	8
<i>Populus talassica</i>	8
<i>Populus x euroamericana</i>	8
<i>Salix acmophylla</i>	8
<i>Salix aongarica</i>	8
<i>Salix turanica</i>	8
<i>Ulmus minor</i>	8
<i>Ulmus pumila</i>	8
Unaspis citri (Comstock)	11
<i>Citrus</i> spp.	11
Venturia nashicola	10
<i>Pyrus bretschneideri</i>	10
<i>Pyrus pyrifolia</i> var. <i>culta</i>	10
<i>Pyrus ussuriensis</i>	10
Xanthomonas oryzae pv. Oryzae	6
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	6
Xanthomonas oryzae pv. Oryzicola	6
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	6

5 Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EKE	Expert Knowledge Elicitation
JRC	European Commission’s Joint Research Centre
PP	Priority Pest
UQP	Union Quarantine pest